

ANALYSIS OF TOMATO SEPAL FUNGAL INFECTION USING HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGING AND DEEP LEARNING

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Introduction - Hyperspectral image processing techniques have significant potential for widespread applications in the food supply chain at multiple scales, from farm level information using remote sensing to individual product quality estimation in factories. For tomatoes, food waste during shipping can be reduced if the fruits susceptible to fungal infection can be identified and sold locally, rather than transported over larger distances, before the infection degrades their quality [1]. Early signs of infection on tomato sepals are related to the loss of moisture and cell degradation on the sepal tips. In this work, 3D convolutional networks are investigated on hyperspectral images of tomato sepals in order to distinguish between the infected and non-infected sepals. In order to understand the model's decisions better, GradCAM is explored to identify the region of the sepal which contributes the most to the model's decision, as well as to analyze the most important wavelengths.

Dataset - The dataset contains hyperspectral images of 101 tomatoes, captured 7 days post-harvest, and kept at 20°C, with relative humidity of 100%. A team of experts determines the infection status of individual sepals. Signs of infection are not easily recognizable, making the classification a challenging task. Sepals with inconsistent labeling are excluded from the experiment. In total, the dataset constitutes 366 sepals from 101 tomatoes, with approximately 17% of sepals infected. Spectral images are captured in the near-infrared range (0.9-1.7 μm) using the Specim FX17 camera. After the elimination of noisy edge bands, 204 channels are used. Black-white and Standard normal variate corrections are applied to calibrate and normalize the image, respectively. Segmentation of individual sepals is done using a selected channel of the PCA transform of the image, followed by top-hat filtering and watershed segmentation. Some segmentation masks are corrected manually. Further, individual sepals are rotated so that their major axis is horizontal, and then they are cropped and zero-padded to the size of 84x36 pixels. The dataset is split in a stratified manner, on the tomato level, to prevent data leakage, into subsets of 222, 74 and 70 sepals (60, 20 and 21 tomatoes) for training, validation and test, respectively.

Model and training - The classification model used in this work is a convolutional neural network proposed in [2]. It consists of 2 layers of 3D convolutions, followed by two fully connected layers, all with ReLU activation function. Dropout and L2 regularizations are utilized to mitigate overfitting. A standard supervised learning approach is used to train the network, with an Adam optimizer and weighted binary cross-entropy loss function. Hyperparameters are tuned using Optuna [3]. GradCAM is utilized for the visualization of activation maps and band importance. A simple image augmentation process is explored, based on rapid operations of indexing the image tensor by flipping it in the spatial domain around the horizontal or vertical axis, both with probability of 0.5, and by shifting it on the spectral axis direction for an offset sampled from the zero-centered normal distribution with standard deviation of 2.

Results and discussion - F1 metric is used to evaluate the classification. Average F1 scores achieved for non-infected and infected samples are 80% and 27% without, and 83% and 45% with data augmentation. Activation maps indicate that the network makes a decision based on the entire sepal area, with an accent on its edges. Two spectral bands are significant, centered at approximately 1.1 μm and 1.5 μm , corresponding to the water absorption bands. Improvement from the use of data augmentation indicates that further exploration of spectral and spatial augmentation can mitigate the effects of class imbalance and the limitation imposed by the small dataset size. Learning approaches based on unsupervised pre-tasks are considered for future work. With increased model performance, more informative activation maps are expected.

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